

THE ESSENCE OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS ON THE BASIS OF AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract: This thesis provides information on what opportunities the integrative approach provides in the professional training of future teachers. There are advantages as well as disadvantages of an integrative approach during the professional training of teachers. Simultaneous education and upbringing in Eastern countries is considered integration. In general, if we consider the world as a whole, any processes taking place in it are inextricably linked. And integration reflects on these relationships.

Key words: science, integrative function, transdisciplinary, consistency, level, policy, educational problems, production, integrated system.

Introduction:

In our time, interest in the problem of integration has increased due to the acceleration of scientific and technical progress, the strengthening of integrative functions in the development of science, education, politics, production, and technology. Simultaneous education and upbringing in Eastern countries is considered integration. In general, if we consider the world as a whole, any processes taking place in it are inextricably linked. And integration reflects on these relationships. Rich experience has been accumulated in the study of integration problems in domestic and foreign pedagogy. In different periods, the task of using interdisciplinarity in the educational process was put forward by Ya. A. Komensky, I. G. Pestalozzi, J. Russo, L. N. Tolstoy, K. D. Ushinsky. The analysis of the literature we are studying shows that I.D. was one of the first to introduce the concept of integration in pedagogy. Zverev and V.N. Maksimova studied and expressed the following opinion: "Integration is the process and result of creating a coherent whole. Science in revealing the problems of interdisciplinary education. LG'. Savenkova said that "Integration is primarily a process that ensures the creativity of teachers and students in a team with changes in educational management technologies."

The process of integration (Latin *integratio* - connection, restoration) is the assembly of previously separate parts and elements of the system into a single whole according to their interdependence and complementarity. By integrating into the pedagogical process, researchers associate the integration of previously separated parts of the development process. they understand one of the aspects.

This process can take place both within an already established system and within a new system

Integration in education is the process of establishing connections between the components of the content within a certain educational system in order to form a holistic view of the world aimed at the development of the learner's personality and self-development. Integration is a process that teaches systematization and simplification of complexity in education. The integration of subjects in modern education is one of the ways to actively search for new pedagogical solutions, to develop the creative potential of pedagogical staff in order to have an effective and reasonable impact on learners. An integrative approach is an approach that helps prepare students to become specialists in their profession. Integration prevents students from getting scattered knowledge, disintegration of their knowledge, ensures that they acquire integrated knowledge and a set of universal values. . The principle of integration includes all components of the educational process, interconnection of all elements of the system, communication between systems, it is the leader in setting the goal, determining the content of education, its forms and methods. The integrative approach means the implementation of the principle of integration in any component of the pedagogical process, ensures the integrity and consistency of the pedagogical process.

Through integration in education, it is possible to teach subjects and interdisciplinary aspects in an integral relationship. This gives students a holistic understanding of the world, the idea that systems are interconnected. In particular, it is clear to all of us that it is possible to develop a child's speech through nature. Natural phenomena, processes taking place in the environment can be explained through poems, stories and plots, which are means of speech development. It forms a strong memory, high imagination, and fluent speech in the child.

Researcher B.S.Abdullayeva also divides interdisciplinary communication into the following types: 1) *meaningful*; 2) *operational*; 3) *methodological*; 4) *organizational*. As noted by B. Abdullayeva¹, skills and competencies form the educational process through thinking operations.

There are three levels of integration.

within the subject - the integration of concepts, knowledge, skills, etc. within individual elements;

¹ Abdullayeva B.S. About types of interdisciplinary communication, 2005, page 14.

interdisciplinary - synthesizing facts, concepts, principles, etc. two or more subjects;

transdisciplinary - a synthesis of the components of the main and additional content of education.

What opportunities does integrated education give us? An integrative approach gives us the following opportunities:

- creates the necessary conditions for the formation of a specialist,
- teaches the learner to perceive the world as a whole,
- educates to be able to act actively in the social and professional sphere,
- sets more demands on students to improve the quality of education and motivates the teacher to continuously improve the quality of teaching, the quality of knowledge,
- different disciplines are interconnected.

Integration allows teachers and students to be involved in an active co-creative process. This is a well-thought-out educational and educational process that helps to revise the general structure of educational organization and prepare students for the process of perception. By teaching to understand and analyze information, students form concepts and ideas about the interaction of all processes in the world as a whole.

In addition, there are disadvantages and negative consequences of the integrative approach. Y. M. Kolegin and O. L. Aleksinko show the negative factors of integration as follows: "a limited number of educational subjects - the content of a large amount of knowledge acquired can be supplemented by reflecting the real view of the world, the interdependence of its parts;" the need to develop very important reading, writing and numeracy skills.

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